

**CONSUMER RESPONSE TO EFFECTIVENESS OF TELEVISION
ADVERTISEMENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE
NGAPATTINAM DISTRICT OF TAMILNADU**

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Abstract

Television is a mirror to a nations personality it can recall the past well upon the present and peep into the future. It is recognized as a medium or mass communication and its significance lies in the fact that it can transmit not only the word, but pictures as well. Television is certainly the potent and popular because, it has an instantaneous and intimate approach and appeal a visual charm or its own and more flexibility and mobility in its converge and mode or operation. To quote water Cronkite “Television can do most communication chores for better than print unit dimensional radio it is better than any other medium.. Television transmission in western countries the introduction In its wake, television brought a new exciting dimension to advertising. The new dimension was not only due to the simple fact that the advertisers, had a new medium. But it is also due to the fact that the advertiser has whole new set of techniques for reaching out to the people, and getting this advertising message across to the people, the advertisers were naturally attracted to this new medium, as it provided an opportunity for presenting live demonstrations or their products and services to a large audience.

Keywords : Television, advertisers, communication, mass, medium

INTRODUCTION

Advertising aims at selling something, a product, a service or an idea. The real aim of advertising is effective communication between marketer and consumer advertising is an art of persuading other to purchase what marketer has the effectiveness of advertising depends upon to what extant advertising message is received and accepted by target audience the effectiveness of an advertising message can be determined through AIDA model of advertising according to A-I-D-A

model of advertising to be effective has to attract attention (A)- SECURE INTERNET (i)-build desire for the product (D)- and family obtain action (A) i.e in the form of sale

Advertising is dynamic it change with changing market changing lifestyle changing methods of distribution and changing pattern of consumption significant development during the past few years include growing awareness that advertising is an institution performing essential social and economic function of late, there has also been a wide spread feeling that advertising as form of communication are meant to exploit the consumer.

Advertising media plays an important role to provide the effective communication between the marketer and consumer. Advertising media is a vehicle which carriers advertisers message to the targeted consumers. There are different types of advertising media available to the advertisers like. Print Media Radio, television and how World Wide Web internet too. Having studies the importance of advertising the researcher like to study introduction of television in India.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bhawna garg (2007) 40 in her article “**Rural marketing study of consumer behavior with reference to hair oil**” analyzed the factors influencing brand choice regarding various products. The researcher observed that television advertisement had deep impact on the minds of consumers in villages. It was found that majority of the respondents had changed their brand of hair oil through television advertisements.

Jullian Villanueva et al (2008)43 in their article, “**The impact of marketing induced verus word-of-mouth customer acquisition on customer equity growth**” analyzed investments or companies could acquire customers through costly but fast-acting marketing investments or through slower but chapter word-of-mouth processes their log term success depends critically on the contributing of each acquired customer to overall equity. An application to a web hosting company reveals that marketing –induced customers add more short-term value word –of-mouth customers add nearly twice as much long value to the firm.

Manish metal (2008)47 in his article “**TV viewing behavior among Indian kids**” analyzed the importance of TV among Indian children have become the most important market segment and the focus of attention for the marketers and advertisers. The knowledge would be helpful in designing promotional strategy to reach the most prominent marketer in the superior way. With these objectives, the author carried out research to understand the TV viewer’s habits of Indian children. The study provides evidence that Indian children like watching TV. They prefer TV viewing over than activities like playing, reading and studying. On an average, they watch 1.20 hours on weekdays, while on weekdays on holidays, the average TV viewing time increases to 2.47 hours.

While children like watching TV the most, they are not found of TV advertisement and do not like watching them. The research also indicates that kids' channels are very popular among children, with Disney channel topping the list of most preferred TV channel.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Advertising has improved tremendously over the last five decades in terms of technical excellence, particularly graphics and copy, but has not made much progress in terms of information relating to the consumer. Good advertising is advertising that sells. Unfortunately most of our advertisements are made with a view to impressing peers other than the consumer.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study revealed that most of the television sets by consumers and effectiveness of the television advertisements with the special reference to the television. The awareness regarding advertising effectiveness has increased in India because of economic and social development. Urbanization state policies and completion among different products, It can be seen that now-a-days there is mass advertising on Electronic products such as television. Washing machine, Refrigerator, Audio system, Personal computers and etc., with a great improvement in advertisement copies. Today Television have become thoroughly respectable throughout the world although favored items change from time to time. There is no decrease in television use but just a shift in emphasis from time to time occurs.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To study the area profile of television market in Nagapattinam.

To highlights the consumer awareness on brands and quality products.

To study the effectiveness of television advertisement on television sets.

To examine the preference of the satellite based television channels.

6. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses were developed for the study

It is proved that there is significant difference in the mean scores on programs ranked in television among respondents.

It is proved that there is significant difference between the level of changes made by advertisement on the socio-economic conditions of the respondents and their age groups.

It is proved that there is significant different between male and female respondents on the level of change made by TV advertisements on the socio-economic condition of the respondents.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the study both primary and secondary data are used. The primary data collected through a well-structured questionnaire prepared and administered to the sample respondent and the primary data also collected through observation. The secondary data was collected from published books, journals and magazines.

7.1 Sample selection

Secondary data were collected from a wide spectrum of sources such as related books, relevant Magazines, published and unpublished sources and government reports.

The Primary data were collected from Television viewers of the district by conducting sample survey using structured, pre-tested interview schedule, adopting convenience sampling model.

7.2 Period of the study

The primary data pertain to a period of 3 years 2012-2013 to 2014-2015 were collected from the sample of 50 television advertisement. The collected data were presented in the form of tables and interview schedule and pre-tested was used to analyses the data and conclusion the analyzed data.

7.3 Sources of data

The primary data, for the study were collected through a structured questionnaire. Questions were prepared, using different sets of scales, namely, nominal and ordinal, as the attributes studied were non parametric.

7.4 Tools used

A well structured Interview schedule was administered in this study to elicit information from the sample TV viewers. The interview schedule was pre-tested with fifty respondents and based on the results obtained, it was slightly modified.

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study was confined to Nagapattinam town. The finding of the study way not be applicable to other rural area. The survey is conducted only from few respondents. Particularly 100 respondents view are taken the product items also restricted i.e., television only.

9. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

It was found that both male and female respondents watching television programs of which male respondents stands majority.

While considering the age factors the age group between 15-25 are mostly watching television programs.

It was observed that the SONY TV set preferred many respondents and followed by LG, BPL and VIDEOCON.

Regarding the awareness about television sets advertisement through media created a good impact.

It was learnt the SUN cable television is preferred almost all the viewers of Nagapattinam

It was observed that the middle age group watching television programmes mostly

Regarding the awareness about television sets selected from quality basic

10. SUGGESTIONS

The other satellite based television like JAYA, SUN MUSIC and sports channels should launch effective programmes like SUN TV programmes to reach the attention at viewers

MNC's (Multi National Company) like Sony, SAMSUNG can improve their advertising campaign regarding with Indian cultural and social aspects I.E., advertising appeal should be planned.

As per the research, teenage and middle age people are potential people who determine the future market potentiality. All the company must give more important to satisfy their expectation (i.e) the advertising activities highly emphasizes to above the change in their expectation.

As the advertising is important aspect of promotional mix, companies have to prefer an effective follow up of the programmes like sales promotion, personal selling should be implemented after executing the advertising.

The VIDEOCON is one the familiar Indian product in the television market it must provide high quality standard product according the changing expectation of consumer. So the R & D (Research & Development) department of VIDEOCON should be encouraged properly.

11. CONCLUSION

The above researches show that the audiences from other media mainly TV

Ability to provide for interactive communication where the advertiser can establish a two-way communication with the consumer.

There is no guarantee that the TV viewers will watch the ad. Message. It is the general tendency that the viewer changes the channels during the advertisement break.

The TV advertisement is attracting the consumer as they like and understand.

Only 43% of teenage people are watching the television

TABLE NO 1.1
TELEVISION SETS BRAND WISE DISTRIBUTION

CLASSIFICATION	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Onida	2	2.5
LG	14	17.5
Philips	6	7.5
Videocon	6	7.5
BPL	12	15
Sansui	4	5
Samsung	12	15
Sony	20	25
JUC	2	2.5
Thomson	2	2.5
TOTAL	80	100

Source: primary data

TABLE NO 1.2
REASON FOR PREFERING PARTICULAR COMPANY SET

DETAILS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Brand Preference	32	40
Low Cost	8	8
Warranty & Service	28	35
Gift & Discount	8	10
Other	4	5
TOTAL	80	100

Source: primary data

TABLE NO : 1.3

AWARENESS OF TELEVISION SETS

DETAILS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Advertisement through media	60	62.5
Friends & Relatives	26	32.5
Neighbours	4	5
TOTAL	80	100

Source: primary data